

D1.3 Scoping phase report: using new data to address R&I policy needs

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Executive Summary

The scoping report summarises the tasks performed within Work Package 1 (WP1), the scoping phase of EURITO. The objective of this work phase was to understand the demand for new innovation indicators and new opportunities to address them with new data sources and methods.

The specific objectives of the scoping phase are as follows:

- To identify the evidence needs of Research and Innovation (R&I) policymakers across the policy cycle, including agenda setting, policy design, implementation and evaluation.
- To identify new data sources which are relevant for R&I policy makers, and to assess and document their general strengths and weaknesses.
- To generate a set of data pilot candidates.

In order to achieve these objectives, the existing literature about evidence needs along the policy life cycle was screened in a first step. Despite the limited literature about the role of indicators in evidence-based policy making, particularly with regard to innovation policy, it has been revealed that:

- Indicators play different roles in the various phases of the policy life cycle;
- The development of innovation policy from market to system failure, and most recently mission orientation, is generating demand for new types of innovation indicators
- The shift in justifying innovation policy requires also expanding the focus of innovation policy instruments from the supply to the demand side, e.g. via public procurement, and generating additional need for innovation indicators;
- There are threats for failure from the very beginning of innovation indicator development to the use of innovation indicators and their impacts along the innovation policy cycle must be considered;
- Innovation indicators must fulfil several requirements in order to gain acceptance among innovation policy makers
- The above-mentioned challenges apply to traditional innovation indicators as well as to new indicators based on new data sources and methods;
- New innovation indicators might also drive innovation policy

Most of these findings have been validated at the Policy Maker Workshop (See Annex 1). The data opportunities have been assessed via an audit of the existing and new available data sources. Both the insights from the demand side, such as the insights from the literature review validated at the Policy Maker Workshop, and the supply side, i.e. the data audit, have been considered in the specification of the following eight data pilots:

- Pilot 1. Emerging Technology Ecosystems, Artificial Intelligence (AI)
- Pilot 2. Nowcasting Business Research and Development (R&D)
- Pilot 3. Technological Change Indicators, Bioenergy
- Pilot 4. Standards as Indicators for The Diffusion of Innovation
- Pilot 5. Evidence Base for Mission-Driven R&I
- Pilot 6. Advanced R&I Funding Analytics
- Pilot 7. Inclusive Innovation
- Pilot 8. Knowledge Exchange

These pilots have been presented and discussed at the knowledge stakeholder workshop, to consider technical issues related to the data generation, processing and analysis. Consequently, some pilots have been narrowed or the scope shifted, e.g. in the case of nowcasting business R&D towards placecasting business R&D. For other pilots, in particular

of the second wave, i.e. Pilot 4 to Pilot 8, the feedback from the workshop was used to their further specification.

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1. Introduction

This report is the finalizing document of WP1, the scoping phase, of the EURITO. It summarizes the various activities within the scoping phase and their major findings. The implications of the scoping phase for the pilot studies are illustrated considering both the demand and the opportunities for new indicators.

The remainder of the deliverable is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 summarizes the objectives of WP1
- Chapter 3 describes and elaborates the applied approach.
- Chapter 4 summarizes the insights of the literature review, which has been delivered in D1.1.
- Chapter 5 presents the auditing of existing R&I data sources and platforms. The results for which have been reported in D1.2.
- Chapter 6 summarizes the first major event, the Policy Maker Workshop. Here, the focus is on the demand for new big data-based indicators.
- Chapter 7 summarizes the outcomes of the Knowledge Stakeholder Workshop focusing on the new opportunities on the supply side. The synthesis of the demand and supply side consideration is illustrated based on the eight pilot studies.
- The final chapter concludes the report.

2. Objectives

The overarching objective of this work package (WP1, Scoping) is to provide a robust foundation of policy and data knowledge for the rest of the project, by developing linkages and accessing relevant information from key stakeholder groups, including R&I policy makers and data researchers. This approach informs the selection of potential data pilots that address policy needs with R&I analytics while harnessing complementarities with existing projects and initiatives.

The specific objectives of this first work package are as follows:

- To identify the evidence needs of R&I policymakers across the policy cycle, including agenda setting, policy design, implementation and evaluation.
- To identify new data sources which are relevant for R&I policy makers, and to assess and document their general strengths and weaknesses.
- To generate a set of data pilot candidates.

This scoping report summarises the findings of the scoping stage including two workshops and makes recommendations about the pilots to be explored in WP2.

3. Approach

In WP1, we have implemented a structured process to engage with policymakers and assess their needs. This has included the coordination of two workshops. In April 2018, we assembled an R&I Policy Stakeholder Group (PSG) involving R&I policymakers from the European Union (EU), European Commission (EC) and other intergovernmental bodies such as, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), who have been invited to provide feedback throughout the project. We have also assembled a Knowledge Stakeholder Group (KSG) involving researchers with expertise in the domain of R&I indicators, and the development of R&I data infrastructures. Representatives include individuals from National Statistical Agencies and Eurostat and were invited to a workshop held in September 2018. Following the recommendation of the Project Officer during the kick-off meeting in February 2018, this workshop was coordinated with a workshop of the sister project Data4Impact and therefore rescheduled to the end of September 2018, instead of June 2018. Consequently, the submission of this deliverable was postponed to the end of November 2018, in order to integrate the insights of the workshop with the KSG in agreement with the Project Officer.

Activities in the scoping phase included identifying the 'burning questions' for R&I policymakers that are unaddressed or poorly addressed by existing datasets and R&I performance indicators. This work package started with a comprehensive literature review. The April 2018 workshop was used to identify priorities for data collection and analysis over the rest of the project. In order to access technical expertise and avoid reinventions of the wheel, we have also established the aforementioned Knowledge Stakeholder Group (KSG). This group provides expert input throughout the project and helps us to connect our activities with other relevant initiatives.

4. Literature Review

In a first step, literature about the needs of policy makers for R&I policy along the policy life cycle were collected, summarised and condensed. The literature review (D1.1) found a large body of studies and publications about innovation indicators, but only few insights about the role of indicators in the policy life cycle. Further, where the role of indicators for policymaking are explored, they are mainly discussed in the context of climate and health policies, with limited studies on indicators for innovation policy.

Indicators play different roles in the various phases of the policy life cycle. It is important to note that the common development of indicators is an important step in policy formulation. The evolution of innovation policy rationales from market to system failure, and most recently mission orientation and the accompanying focus on demand-side-oriented policy instruments, generate new demand for innovation indicators as current indicators are inadequate, because they are not covering new emerging technologies or outdated to the increased dynamics in science and technology. There are many potential opportunities and threats of failure from the very beginning of the innovation indicator development process (from deciding on the use of innovation indicators) to their impacts along the innovation policy cycle, for instance, their potential misuse and misinterpretation. It was recommended EURITO tackles those threats. Future innovation indicators based on new data sources to be developed by EURITO must fulfil several requirements including satisfying the 'RITO' framework of relevance, inclusion, trust, timeliness, and openness to gain acceptance among innovation policymakers.

The findings highlighted in the literature review will be considered when scaling up and implementing the selected innovation pilot indicators. Overall, the findings of the literature review will guide EURITO to develop indicators fulfilling the RITO criteria.

5. Audit of Existing R&I Data Sources and Platforms

The audit of existing R&I data sources and platforms has been documented in the audit report (D2.1) describing the data auditing framework developed for the EURITO project. In doing this, it specifically considered the work of ongoing R&I data projects, platforms and initiatives to avoid a duplication of work and to build on these previous projects.

The audit framework developed in D2.1 consists of four interrelated components:

1. Conceptual anchoring phase;
2. Basic audit of data sources allowing for an assessment of minimum viability to explore the concept of interest;
3. Identification of pilot ideas, and
4. Advanced audit framework to be carried out following the selection of pilots.

Figure 1: EURITO Data Audit

This four-phase approach aims to provide enough structure to guide the search for new data, while also allowing for adequate flexibility to explore emergent concepts and ideas. The division of the main auditing steps into ‘basic’ and ‘advanced’ phases permits a more efficient use of time and resources by ensuring that only those data sources which are linked to a pilot idea are explored in more depth.

The auditing approach outlined in D1.2 served as the basis for the next phases of the EURITO project, underpinning both the conceptual and analytical progression toward the development of indicators that are relevant, inclusive, trusted, timely, and open. In particular, the results of D1.2 acted as input for the workshop with the experts of the Knowledge Stakeholder Group (KSG), who have participated in the development of an R&I data infrastructure (in particular through EC funded projects including the Community Innovation Surveys), to discuss their experiences both related to data collection, provision and maintenance, as well as usage by policy makers in order to identify success factors, barriers and lessons learned to be considered for the further work packages.

6. Policy Maker Workshop

The results of the literature review and the audit of existing R&I data sources and platforms was as input for a Policy Maker Workshop organized in April 2018 in Brussels at the European Commission. The objective was to discuss and validate a conceptual model including the various needs in the different stages of the R&I policy cycle, existing data limitations and new data opportunities.

This included exploring questions such as:

- Which additional, feasible innovation metrics would be desirable to obtain?
- How are data used to inform R&I policy right now?
- Which additional data sources should be taken into account to generate more inclusive, trusted and open R&I indicators?
- What are priorities for data collection and analysis?
- What are concrete wishes to close existing data gaps with relevant, inclusive, transparent and open indicators?
- What are the 'pain points' and questions for which current data are limited or inadequate?
- What are possible challenges, e.g. legal concerns, related to new indicators?

The objective of the Policy Maker Workshop was to enter in conversation with policymakers to learn their impressions on both, the existing sets of indicators and their demand for a future generation of indicators on innovation. The policy maker audience was encouraged to share their wider concerns on issues connected with the project such as the role of data in formulating, implementing and evaluating innovation policy or the methodology for obtaining innovation data.

To organise the dialogue, the workshop had two parts. The first was focused on the status quo of the current system of indicators and the second was oriented towards a prospective analysis of what should be added, retained or removed when building a new system of indicators. Policy makers were split across five tables. Each table was presented with the same questions as a starting point and in each table the debate was accompanied by members of the EURITO project consortium acting as moderators.

One way to summarise the main feedback obtained from policymakers was to present their contributions in a modified SWOT in the following way (W-O-S-T):

Weaknesses of the status quo	Opportunities for the new system
<i>Shortcoming of the current system that should be addressed</i>	<i>Ways in which a new generation of innovation indicators might address the existing limitations</i>
Strengths of the status quo	Threats of the new system
<i>Desirable attributes that should be preserved</i>	<i>Risks that are to be avoided when building up a new system</i>

Table 1: Weaknesses, Opportunities, Strengths, Threats - Structure

Based on the moderators' and rapporteur's notes of the sessions the following W-O-S-T summarises the main messages that emerged from the policy-maker session.

Weaknesses of the status quo	Opportunities for the new system
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The time lag between reality and measurement; it can be up to 2 or 2.5 years. • Inability to detect emerging innovation trends. • Indicators fail to cover the whole picture, there are blind spots (in the geographical and industry dimensions) of existing innovation activities and communities. In particular, three coverage gaps identified in: social innovation, public sector and geographic granularity of data. • There is the burden of response in obtaining some data (e.g. surveys); this intensifies bias/coverage problems. • The current system is not helpful when assessing the impact of a particular project or a public call. Private companies very rarely rely on the existing indicators for impact assessment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of resolving the problems of time lag, coverage and blind spots. • If the data are open and sufficiently micro, new possibilities emerge of doing collaborative / network analysis of data. This could trigger and sustain iterations with new stakeholders, currently under the 'official' radar; this decentralisation might help identify emerging trends. • The effort may go beyond setting up a new battery of indicators and contribute to a conversation on how policymakers and society think about innovation. • The new system will work better as a complement (not substitute) to the current set of indicators; this would facilitate acceptance by stakeholders and boost the potential of the project.
Strengths of the status quo	Threats of the new system
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has established widely accepted standards. • Long time series allow for temporal and cross-section analysis; these are the typical exercises policy makers ask for. • Politicians have gotten used to the current "simple" data and outputs. New information and analysis should need to be "translatable" to the old metrics and mindsets, at least in the short run. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of data quality and limited reliability/traceability of new indicators. • Big data might produce "too much" data; it will be necessary to select and focus – this is not trivial • Peril of succumbing to "data enthusiasm": producing rich and complex analysis, but which are difficult to interpret, generalize and replicate. • Data protection and legal issues may appear in decentralized setups of information gathering. Differences of legal standards across countries. • Acceptance and use of new indicators by policy makers will come only after researchers use and adopt them; politicians are considered generally to act as "followers" rather than as "innovators" in the use of new data and analytics. • <i>Recommendation:</i> It will be key to set up credible validation procedures (e.g. triangulation) that persuade users and stakeholders.

Table 2: Weaknesses, Opportunities, Strengths, Threats - Content

Another illustration of participants' assessment of strengths and weaknesses on the one hand and opportunities and threats, on the other hand, is the SWOT presented in Figure 2. The strength of the existing indicators appear to be mostly in the agenda-setting and implementation phases, whereas the weaknesses seem to concentrate on the implementation and evaluation phases. The opportunities and threats related to new indicators are perceived in all stages of the policy cycle.

Figure 2: Assessment of strengths and weaknesses of traditional indicators, as well as of new RITO indicators across different stages of the policy cycle.

7. Knowledge Stakeholder Workshop

The “New Data for R&I Policy Workshop” (“Workshop”) was the last step of the scoping phase and one of the first steps in the exploration stage. The goal of the workshop was, on the one hand, to provide data-driven researchers with an opportunity to share their experiences and, on the other hand, to provide the project team with external inputs on how to advance better the project by looking closely at the various pilots developed so far.

The EURITO New Data for R&I Policy Workshop took place on Tuesday, September 25, 2018, in the premises of the European Commission, Brussels. The full-day workshop invited a diverse set of actors supporting data-driven decision making (like data developers and researchers covering R&I policy, industry and the public sector) to share their experiences on data infrastructure and data pipelines.

By making use of the collective intelligence and varied background/skillsets of participants, EURITO aimed at identifying relevant data, tools, methods that might be integrated into the development of the EURITO pilots that were presented during the event.

The event was attended by more than thirty people from all over Europe, including Research and Data scientists in the domain of new R&I indicators and data infrastructures. These experts came from National Statistical Agencies and industry, other EC-funded projects, the European Commission (policymakers from DG RTD, JRC and REA) and the OECD. The workshop presented eight exploratory pilots, at various stages of concretion and development. The key goal of the workshop was to get constructive feedback from the audience about the content and approaches applied in the pilots, particularly regarding technical details, but also related to their policy relevance. The input obtained from the participants contribute to make better informed decisions about these eight pilots, such as: Which are the most promising pilots to scale up in the next stage of the project? How to improve the specifications of the pilots? Which (i) data, (ii) analytical tools, and (iii) ways of visualising data are better suited for each individual pilot?

The participants provided valuable insights into the current needs for data infrastructure and the efficient functioning of the data pipeline that can help identify success factors, barriers and lessons learnt to validate and review the pilots being developed by the project.

The main general messages and conclusions that emerged from the workshop are synthesized here. Further information about the issues that emerged across the various discussions of the different pilots can be found in Annex 2.

- **Problem Solving vs. Unknown Unknowns.** Some pilots are primarily developed by answering one or more specific questions regarding innovation activity in areas and/or industries. For this purpose, typically Natural Language Processing algorithms are used to look for a predefined set of keywords (and related concepts or patterns). This keeps the pilot focused and allows to provide very detailed information and/or visualizations. For instance: “In which EU cities / regions has been the R&I activity in Artificial Intelligence more dynamic?” or “What is the rate and evolution of technological change in a given field X”? However, although this is a very valuable input, in certain cases, it would be more useful to know what the “right questions” to ask or/and the “right keywords” to search for.
- **From Descriptive to Predictive.** The likelihood of transforming pilots from a purely descriptive exercise towards one with some predictive power is an important issue to consider. This was a central question for the pilot on predicting future R&D expenditures. Showing that the new generation of indicators improves the current set of indicators in this dimension might be useful to convince policymakers and the data community.

- **Simple, Compatible Indicators.** A winning strategy when proposing a new generation of indicators would be to position them as complements (or compatible) rather than substitutes of the existing sets of data. This indeed was also one of the key takeaways from the Policymakers' Workshop in April. In practice, this seems to suggest that it is preferable that new indicators are simple in construction and rely on solid primary data. This appeared particularly in the discussion about the pilot about standards as innovation indicators. A corollary is that it might be useful, when considering a possible new indicator stemming from a given pilot, how the metadata (statistical specifications in terms of universe, sample, coverage, nomenclature, etc.) would look like.
- **Reconsideration of the Concept of “Impact” of R&D.** A general topic that emerged in the discussion of the pilots being still in an early phase, like on mission-driven research and innovation or inclusive innovation, was the issue, somehow abstract but of crucial importance, of defining properly the impact or outcome of R&I beyond the purely economic dimension. In addition to economic returns, successful innovation can foster diversity in research teams, help address social missions and contribute to more inclusive communities, enhance knowledge exchanges that appear to be minor initially, but that may develop to become more substantial and relevant.

8. Implications for the selection and specification of data pilots

While preparing and drafting the proposal the consortium had already started developing some R&I policy relevant pilot ideas to focus on during the project. Some of these involved datasets and methods the consortium members had previously worked with. This is the list of pilots outlined in the proposal:

- **Nowcasting Business R&D Investment**
- **Measuring Open Digital Innovation in Europe**
- **Informal Innovation Networks in Europe**
- **Predicting Business Innovation Outcomes in The CORDA Database**
- **R&I Performance Indicators for Humanities and Social Sciences**
- **Analysis and Development of Non-Conventional Metrics Derived from Scientific Production**
- **Open Standard Adoption as A Systems Innovation**
- **The Impact of Open Data Repositories**
- **The Micro-Geography of Innovation**

Based on the inputs from the literature review about the evidence needs of R&I policymakers along the policy life cycle and the audit of new R&I Data source the initial planned eight pilots have been modified and adjusted. We also drew on an experimental wiki survey of R&I policy questions to capture potential new pilot ideas as well as to rank those which had arisen from the original grant agreement and the policymaker workshop.¹

All this feedback informed the first drafts of the pilots presented at the knowledge stakeholder workshop. In addition, the feedback from the participating experts has been eventually integrated in the following summary of the demand side, the policy maker perspective, and supply side, the data opportunities, justifying each pilot. This chapter presents the interface to the second work package, the exploration phase.

Pilot 1: Emerging Technology Ecosystems, Artificial Intelligence

- **Demand Side**
 - Policymakers want to understand the development and evolution of emerging technologies, like artificial intelligence, with transformative potential.
 - These technologies are hard to monitor in aggregated, lagged databases organised around standardised taxonomies.
 - The successful development of emerging technologies depends on the presence of a sectoral system of innovation providing knowledge, finance and skills - but data about all these different features are generally split in silos and hard to integrate.
- **Supply Side**
 - Many traditional data sources such as scientific papers, patents and information about research grants contain textual information that can be queried to identify mentions of emerging technologies, like artificial intelligence.
 - There are new social media and web data sources that shed light on less traditional features of sectoral innovation systems such as informal networking and open innovation.

¹ The survey yielded 320 votes from 19 user sessions over a period of nine days. Knowledge Exchange and Standards were ranked as the most popular pilots, and two additional ideas were suggested. Unfortunately, given the low response rate and difficulty to formulate consistency in survey questions, the results have not contributed significantly to the final selection of pilots.

- Machine learning methods can be used to project classifications from one data source, for example the industries where businesses operate, into another, for example the industries for which an emerging technology application is relevant, helping to create connections between previously siloed data sources and concepts.

Pilot 2: Nowcasting Business R&D

- **Demand Side**
 - Business R&D is among the most fundamental innovation indicators that policy-makers make use of.
 - Current collection of business R&D data relies on survey data, the results of which are published several months or years after data has been collected.
 - Policy-makers who attended the April 2018 workshop indicated that a 'nowcasted' indicator, i.e. one which is real time or nearly so, would be highly valuable.
- **Supply Side**
 - New types of data on innovation activities can serve as predictors (e.g. open source software development, interaction with startups based on analysis of press releases etc.). From these, we will attempt to identify 'hidden' types of innovation investment that influence R&D activity.
 - These new data sources can be analysed using machine learning models to predict activity, thereby developing a 'nowcasted' indicator.

Pilot 3. Technological Change Indicators, Bioenergy

- **Demand Side**
 - The evolution of technology is poorly understood, and policymakers require better insights about the speed of technological change in different fields of knowledge in order to better target funding.
 - Simply looking at the volume of papers, patents and other outputs is not enough to understand the nature of technological change (e.g. incremental vs radical changes).
 - The overall speed of change has increased, and we need better indicators to keep track of fields that can evolve and reach maturity in as little as 5 years.
- **Supply Side**
 - New analytical methods derived from network science allow to generate transparent metrics to quantify technological changes as a function of combinatorial reconfiguration of the R&D outputs.
 - Text mining techniques are more affordable and scalable, making possible to analyse large amounts of documents.
 - Patents, scientific publications and publicly funded projects generate large amounts of documents that can be mined to discover patterns.

Pilot 4. Standards as Indicators for the Diffusion of Innovation

- **Demand Side**
 - There is a strong need for indicators showing the implementation of innovations as a justification for public funding of R&D.

- The majority of indicators, like patents, is focused on product innovations, whereas process innovations are often kept secret. Consequently, there is a specific need for indicators of process innovations.
- The OECD/Eurostat (2018) integrated standards in the 4th edition of the Oslo Manual, e.g. both as information sources for innovation, but more important regarding companies' ability to demonstrate that their product or business process innovations meet relevant industry or market standards as innovation objective.
- OECD (2016) integrated standards, certification and accreditation as one dimension in its SME Policy Index.
- Standardisation is an important policy tool for DG GROW and DG CONNECT at the EU level, but also for several ministries at Member States level.

- **Supply Side**

- International standards released by ISO are approved in a consensus process involving more than 150 countries.
- ISO collects since the 1990s data about the diffusion of certifications of important management standards.
- Data for all EU Member States differentiated by sectors are available.
- Data for more than additional 100 countries are available.
- The development of an indicator, which can be integrated in the set for indicators for the European Innovation Scoreboard, is possible.

Pilot 5. Evidence Base for Mission-Driven R&I

- **Demand Side**

- Following a broader trend within innovation policy to more explicitly engage with issues such as environmental sustainability, mission-orientation has become a focal point for future R&I policymaking at European level.
- In spring 2018, the European Commission published a report commissioned by the Minister for Research, Science and Innovation on a 'problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth' (European Commission 2018), which draws heavily on the mission-orientation framework.
- The recognition that achieving missions will require new ways of developing partnerships across industries and domains is accompanied by a need for new types of data, e.g. types of collaborations, missing links, which new data sources and analytics are well-placed to provide.

- **Supply Side**

- By combining multiple open and proprietary datasets capturing different facets of the R&I ecosystem in Europe, e.g. publications, research funding data, company activity, etc., we will be able to develop a far richer picture of the landscape around a particular mission.
- The use of interactive visualisations will provide a powerful platform for actors from all parts of the system to engage with, allowing them to identify potential partnerships, overlaps, complementarities, etc.

Pilot 6. Advanced R&I Funding Analytics

- **Demand Side**

- A wide array of gaps in current funding analytics were identified through stakeholder engagement workshops, including the propensity to simplify complex phenomena to a one-size-fits-all formula resulting in one number as

an output. For instance, certain bibliometric analyses may not fully reflect the citation differences across disciplines.

- Additionally, the trickle-down effects or longer-term impacts of research, e.g. commercial uptake by industry, are not captured in simplistic metrics of scientific publications or their citations.
- **Supply Side**
 - Building on previous research in the area of multidisciplinary, this pilot will further develop metrics around the extent to which diverse viewpoints can contribute to successful outputs such as papers and patents.
 - The pilot will make use of European research funding in CORDIS to predict project outputs in SESAM (the European Commission's online reporting tool for research and innovation projects).
 - The pilot will also explore the use of natural language processing algorithms to project abstracts to assess the 'convergence' in language used for project teams (who may come from different fields, industries, etc.), and to see whether convergence predicts the success of the project.

Pilot 7. Inclusive Innovation

- **Demand Side**
 - As policymakers around the world grapple with increasingly volatile social backlashes fuelled in part by rising inequalities and populism, there is an urgent need to explore the ways in which R&I systems can contribute to solutions. One of the approaches that has been put forth in this regard is to make R&I ecosystems more inclusive, with inclusivity being defined as increasing participation from formerly excluded ascribed groups, e.g. gender, ethnicity, or by region. Other axes of inclusivity of interest to innovation policy-makers include efforts to stimulate productivity within lagging industries.
- **Supply Side**
 - New data sources and analytics provide ample opportunities to explore the inclusiveness of the R&I landscape in more depth. For instance, data of increased granularity provide deeper insights into place-based disparities, while new algorithms are capable of classifying gender and ethnicity of people within these systems.
 - Despite increased availability to explore the various dimensions of inclusivity, a challenge arises that this concept (and the types of indicators which may ultimately be of interest to stakeholders) are highly-context specific.

Pilot 8. Knowledge Exchange

- **Demand Side**
 - There is an increasing agreement that different types of "linkages", e.g. collaboration and information exchange, are a crucial element when it comes to innovation ecosystems. For example, they are explicitly mentioned in the European Innovation Scoreboard.
 - Despite the relevance of linkages few indicators exist that are explicitly developed to measure this dimension. The few that exist mostly focus on a simple count of collaborations.
 - Marnix Surgeon, EC's Deputy Head of the Unit 'Analysis and monitoring of national research policies' explicitly encouraged us to look into linkage indicators
- **Supply Side**

- Open relational data containing information about citations/references, collaborations, events and co-affiliations is increasingly available and can help to map linkages at multiple levels.
- Most of the available open data of this kind can be aggregated and anonymised before ingestion, avoiding GDPR concerns.
- New data analytics and visualisation techniques allow to create intuitive and transparent indicators.

Summarizing the demand side related to the eight pilots, we reveal the following general trends, which have been already expressed at the policy maker workshop. In general, policy makers are increasingly interested in more timely information, e.g. about R&D, which is not available via traditional company surveys, like the Community Innovation Survey. This demand is becoming more severe due to faster rates of change in science and technology, which are in general still not well understood. In particular, understanding the development and evolution of emerging technologies with transformative potential is very important due to their high potential impact and the increasingly competitive pressure among countries and consequently policy makers. However, these emerging technologies are difficult to monitor by relying on isolated databases structured according to already existing and well-established classifications. In addition to new emerging technologies, new forms of research and innovation, like open innovation, are challenging policy makers, e.g. for the development of new funding mechanism. These new innovation paradigms are based on collaboration and information exchange, consequently data and indicators about linkages between different actors and activities are becoming more important, e.g. for the identification of possible recipients of funding. Furthermore, policy makers need not only better indicators about emerging fields in science and technology, there is also a strong need for indicators showing both the short and the long-term impact of public funding of R&D to justify further public funding. Finally, new policy initiatives, like mission-orientation, requires new information for developing new types of partnerships as well as the new objective of using innovation to achieve inclusiveness.

At the supply side, we can observe the following trends. First, already existing data sources, like the certifications of international standards, are becoming more important, because standards and standardisation has been acknowledged as being important for innovation. Second, the combination of already existing data sources is being enabled by new data processing technologies and allowing the mapping and analyses of whole R&I ecosystems. Third, the content of these sources, like scientific papers or patents, and their related metadata, like authors, their affiliations and references, can be analysed by using sophisticated methods of text mining and machine learning. Fourthly, this information allows to map linkages at multiple levels. In addition to the analysis of existing sources by using new advanced methodologies being able to process big data, like full texts of scientific papers or patents, new social media and web data sources are available. In particular, increased granularity related to scientific and technological areas, stakeholders or regions is possible. They are able to shed light on less traditional features of innovation systems such as informal networking, open innovation and open source software development.

Overall, the selection of the pilots is reflecting both the insights of the literature review and the audit of possible data sources as well as the discussions at the Policy Maker Workshop and the Knowledge Stakeholder Workshop.

9. Conclusion

The scoping report as concluding output of the scoping phase summarises the findings of the various tasks performed, i.e. literature review, audit of data sources and the consultations with the demand side, the policy makers, and the supply side, the knowledge stakeholders generating, processing and analysing data. These insights have already informed the selection and specifications of the eight data pilots and will play an important role during their implementation and scaling up.

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Annex 1: Workshop 1 Report

EURITO Policy Maker Workshop, 17 April 2018, Brussels

WORKSHOP REPORT

published on 11 May 2018

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Disclaimer: The contents of this report are the sole responsibility of the authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Union.

Report of the EURITO Policy Maker Workshop

17 April 2018

The EURITO Policy Maker Workshop took place on Tuesday 17 April in the premises of the European Commission, Brussels. As a day-long interactive workshop of current and future Research and Innovation (R&I) indicator needs of national, European and international policymakers, it was the first workshop under the Horizon 2020 project EURITO led by Nesta (UK) with Consortium partners of Fraunhofer FOKUS (Germany), Technical University of Denmark, DTU (Denmark) and Cotec (Spain). Guiding the discussions, the Consortium presented its findings from the literature review on existing indicator use and limitations, and framed for discussion new data opportunities along the different stages of the R&I policy cycle for input and insight from participants. Almost thirty participants ranging from senior representatives from national ministries (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Denmark, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Spain and Sweden) to policymakers from the European Commission (DG RTD, DG GROW, JRC and REA) and the OECD provided valuable insight into the current status quo and future needs of R&I performance indicators using new sources of big and open data that will feed into the next steps of the project, namely the Exploration Phase.

This report consists of two parts: the first section provides a summary report of discussions by the workshop Rapporteur, followed by a more detailed report on presentations, discussions and findings of the day.

We encourage participants and those interested in the development of EURITO to stay connected by subscribing to the EURITO Newsletter (through this [link](#)), keeping abreast of blog posts on the [project webpage](#), and/or staying in touch via the several EURITO social media channels ([Medium](#); [Twitter](#)). You also reach out to the Consortium directly by emailing info@eurito.eu.

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Rapporteur's Summary
Ramon Xifré, COTEC

The Policy Maker Workshop forms one component of the first stage of the EURITO project, the Scoping Phase. The goal of this phase is to better define the needs and wants regarding a new set of R&I indicators from the viewpoint of the key users: policymakers and related actors. Findings are to guide the development of this 3-year project in pilot development, scale-up and fit-for-purpose, usable and useful visualisations. The goal of the workshop was to gain first-hand insight from policymakers on both existing sets of indicators and their desires for a future generation of indicators. Participants were encouraged to share their wider concerns on issues connected with the project such as the role of data in formulating, implementing and evaluating R&I policy or the methodology for obtaining data.

To organize the dialogue, the workshop consisted of two parts. The first session was focused on the status quo of the current use of R&I indicators and the second oriented to a prospective analysis of what should be added, retained or removed when building a new system of indicators. Policymakers were split up randomly in five tables to stimulate dialogue. Each table was confronted with the same questions as a starting point and in each table the debate was accompanied by members of the EURITO project consortium acting as moderators.

One way to summarize the main feedback obtained from policymakers in the session is to present their contributions in a modified SWOT in the following way (W-O-S-T):

<p>Weaknesses of the status quo <i>Shortcomings of current indicators that should be addressed</i></p>	<p>Opportunities of new R&I indicators based on big data <i>Ways in which a new generation of R&I indicators might address the existing limitations</i></p>
<p>Strengths of the status quo <i>Desirable attributes that should be preserved</i></p>	<p>Threats of new R&I indicators <i>Risks that are to be avoided when building up new indicators</i></p>

Drawing from the moderators' notes as well as from my own take of the session I propose the following W-O-S-T to summarize the main messages that emerged from the policy makers workshop.

<p>Weaknesses of the status quo</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The time lag between reality and measurement; it can be up to 2 or more years. • Inability to detect emerging innovation trends. • It does not cover the whole picture, there are blind spots (in the geographical and industry dimensions) of existing innovation activities and communities. In particular, three coverage gaps identified in: social innovation, public sector and regions. • There is the burden of responsiveness in obtaining some data; this intensifies bias/coverage problems. • The current system is limited for assessing the impact of a particular project or a public policy decision. Private companies needing data for similar reasons very rarely rely on the existing indicators for impact assessment. 	<p>Opportunities for new R&I indicators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of resolving the problems of time lag, coverage and blind spots. • If the data are open and sufficiently granular, new possibilities emerge of doing collaborative / network analysis of data. This could trigger and sustain iterations with new stakeholders, currently under the official radar; this “new granularity” might help identify emerging trends. • The effort may go beyond setting up a new battery of indicators and contribute to a conversation on how policymakers and society think about innovation; i.e. it may bring inputs to the agenda setting stage. • The new system will better work as a complementary (not substitute) of the current set of indicators; this would facilitate acceptance by stakeholders and boost the potential of the project.
<p>Strengths of the status quo</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has established widely accepted standards. • Long time series allow for temporal and cross-section analysis; these are the typical evidence policy makers ask for. • Politicians are familiar with the current system. New information and analysis need to be “translatable” to the old metrics and mindsets, at least in the short run. 	<p>Threats of new R&I indicators based on big data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of data quality and limited reliability/ traceability of new indicators. • Big data might produce “too much” data; it will be necessary to select and focus – this is not trivial. • Peril of succumbing to “data enthusiasm”: producing rich and complex analyses, but which are difficult to interpret, generalize and replicate. • Data protection and legal issues may appear in decentralized setups of information gathering. Differences of legal standards across countries despite GDPR. • Acceptance and use of new indicators by policy makers will come only after the innovation communities use and adopt them; politicians are considered generally to act as “followers” rather than as “innovators”. • <i>Recommendation:</i> It will be key to set up credible validation procedures (triangulation) that persuade users and stakeholders.

Report of the Day

The Workshop commenced with introductory remarks from Marnix Surgeon, Deputy Head, Analysis and Monitoring of National Research and Innovation Policies, DG RTD on the European policy context of opportunities using big data as R&I indicators, followed by short remarks by Caroline Paunov, Directorate for Science, Technology, and Industry of the OECD on relevant OECD projects concerning new data and semantic technologies in R&I policy. Caroline Paunov highlighted the promise and challenge of semantic analysis in the R&I policy ecosystem and current exercises such as exploring text proximity of discoveries and inventions contained in patent data to trace knowledge transfer.

The Consortium led presentations to guide the morning discussion groups with an overview of the EURITO project by Juan Mateos-Garcia, Nesta, and project's lead Scientific Coordinator. EURITO is about the digital transformation of R&I policy and the substantial opportunities of the new generation of **relevant, inclusive, timely, trusted and open (RITO)** R&I indicators using new sources of big and open data that can enable this process. It is about what we measure, how we measure and how we create value from this measure. Professor Knut Blind, from Fraunhofer FOKUS, leading the Scoping Phase and co-task leader with Cotec of the Policy Stakeholder Workshop, continued the Consortium presentations with findings of the literature review on using indicators in general and also along the Innovation Policy Life Cycle. Then, participants were randomly assigned a Discussion Group, and with guidance by Consortium Moderators in groups of 6 to 7 policymakers and related experts, they were encouraged to interactively discuss needs and challenges framed according to 'RITO', or indeed any other dimensions the project may have missed.

EURITO Policy Maker Workshop Discussion Groups during the Morning Session
Summarising the discussions, the Moderators recounted the diversity of the topics discussed starting from the benefits of the currently used indicators, like

comparability and time series and then moving to concrete wishes ranging from indicators to show linkages, cross-fertilisation of existing data sources such as publications and patents, with new ways of traceability and acknowledgement; thinking more of proxy data sources that could be used to 'nowcast' outcomes of interest; to have good visualisations and better measures of impact (for instance, not only economic impact but also societal impact; impact over longer time horizons; as well as impact on granular levels). Some also commented on the weakness of the current status quo, for instance, the complex levels of using information. Indicators are used differently for evaluating specific policy measures compared to indicators used for agenda-setting. For instance, indicators developed for agenda-setting should focus on what matters at the general level, whereas indicators used to evaluate specific policy instruments have to be more specific.

The afternoon discussions focused on the new opportunities related to R&I indicators based on big data and the possible trade-offs that should be managed. Guiding the discussions, Pedro Parraguez Ruiz, DTU and Chantale Tippett, Nesta, continued the Consortium presentations. Pedro Parraguez Ruiz highlighted the opportunities presented by RITO R&I indicators using new data and analytics, namely the opportunity to answer a richer range of questions and provide complementary new perspectives; examples of [AMICa](#) and [Arloesiadur](#) projects developed by DTU and Nesta respectively were provided. Chantale Tippett presented pilot samples using new data to study innovation with the aim to upgrade the toolbox of innovation indicators for policymakers. Following the format of the morning session, participants in different groups discussed ideas and opportunities as well as challenges and issues of new R&I indicators.

Pedro Parraguez Ruiz presenting in the afternoon session

Findings from afternoon discussions show not only examples of existing innovative uses of big data for policymaking (such as combining credit card data with cell phone data, analysing networks), examples of new data sources (e.g. Mendeley, Orbis, ORCID), but also opportunities to get value out of existing data, like by the triangulation of various data and by iterations in developing new data. Challenges are creating trust (on how data is collected) and how to interpret data in its specific context, e.g. taking regional diversity into account. Finally, it has to be considered how the R&I indicator debate is brought into the agenda of innovation policy makers. Is it the policy agenda driving the development of new indicators or are new indicators driving the policy agenda?

Poster showing strengths and weaknesses of traditional indicators, as well as of new RITO indicators across different stages of the Policy Cycle.

As closing statements, Knut Blind provided a summary of findings:

- Existing indicators have their value, which can be increased by further harmonization, but in particular by interlinking them with new data;
- Tracing stakeholders within the innovation system by using new data sources will lead to a better grasp of the impact of R&D policy;
- More collaboration between different data providers, but also more transparency about data collection is needed;
- Challenge of attributing both existing, but in particular the new indicators to the different Policy Life Cycle stages.

Juan Mateos-Garcia thanked the participants for their invaluable contributions and reiterated the project's promise to enabling R&I policy with better decisions with bigger (and better measured) impacts. Next steps will be deciding the pilots to focus on (the sorts of characteristics to be fed into the pilots, the choice of specific datasets), to be followed by the generation of prototypes and then selecting some based on evaluating trade-offs for scale-up. Juan Mateos-Garcia commented that the day's discussions shed light on how the aims of the project are not merely technical, but also about the integration of new indicators in innovation policy - how evidence is used, how stakeholders are organised within the ecosystem - which make the project more complicated than the initial design but undoubtedly will provide important insights to increase the impact of EURITO.

The EURITO Consortium. From left Agzam Idrisov, Pedro Parraguez, Paloma Martin - Project Officer - Research Executive Agency (REA), Aleix Pons, Juan Mateos-Garcia, Professor Anja Maier, George Richardson, Chantale Tippett, Joel Klinger, Knut Blind, Minji Song and Ainara Zubillaga.

EURITO New Data for R&I Policy Workshop

WORKSHOP REPORT

The EURITO New Data for R&I Policy Workshop took place on Tuesday, September 25, 2018, in the premises of the European Commission, Brussels. The full-day workshop invited a diverse set of actors supporting data-driven decision making (like data developers and researchers covering R&I policy, industry and the public sector) to share their experiences on data infrastructure and data pipelines.

By making use of the collective intelligence and varied background/skillsets of participants, EURITO aimed at identifying relevant data, tools, methods that might be considered integrating into the development of the EURITO pilots that were presented during the event.

The event was attended by more than thirty people from all over Europe, including Research and Data scientists in the domain of new R&I indicators and data infrastructures. These experts came from National Statistical Agencies and industry, other EC-funded projects, the European Commission (policymakers from DG RTD, JRC and REA) and the OECD. They provided valuable insights into the current needs for data infrastructure and the efficient functioning of the data pipeline, in order to identify success factors, barriers and lessons learnt to validate and review the pilots being developed by the project, that will feed into the next steps of the project, namely the Exploration Phase.

During the EURITO workshop, it was discussed ideas of data collection, analysis and visualization for the backend of the data pipeline and infrastructure for decision-making (data production/collection, analysis and interpretation, as well as usage by decision-makers). And also, interesting ideas for collaborative projects with the invited researchers came up.

This report provides the final agenda, list of participants, and a summary report of discussions by the workshop rapporteur, followed by a more detailed report on discussions and findings of each of the pilots' working groups.

We encourage participants and those interested in the development of EURITO to stay connected by subscribing to the EURITO Newsletter (through [this link](#)) or following EURITO project resources and social media channels through our new website www.eurito.eu.

You also reach out to the Consortium directly by emailing info@eurito.eu.

The EURITO Consortium:

Technical University
of Denmark

Documents

Working Documents

1. [High Level Matrix of all 8 EURITO Pilots](#)
2. Pilot Specification Notes including key questions/issues for discussion, a list of relevant material:

Wave 1

- 2.1. [Pilot 1](#) Emergent technology ecosystems, AI (led by Nesta)
- 2.2. [Pilot 2](#) Nowcasting business R&D (led by Nesta with input from COTEC)
- 2.3. [Pilot 3](#) Technological change indicators, bioenergy (led by DTU)
- 2.4. [Pilot 4](#) Standards as indicators for the diffusion of innovation (led by Fraunhofer)

Wave 2

- 2.5. [Pilot 5](#) Evidence base for mission-driven R&I (led by Nesta)
- 2.6. [Pilot 6](#) Advanced R&I funding analytics (led by Nesta)
- 2.7. [Pilot 7](#) Inclusive Innovation (led by Nesta)
- 2.8. [Pilot 8](#) Knowledge/exchange flow indicators, healthtech (led by DTU)

[Consortium presentation](#) and [Case Studies](#)

Background Documents

- **“The EURITO Data Audit Framework (EDAF)”** Our novel approach to the data auditing process creating a robust foundation for the use of data and indicators along the policy life cycle. In this issue, we are delighted to share:
 - “Audit of new R&I data” ([Link](#))
 - “A (structured) quest for research and innovation policy questions and data” [blog](#)

More in EURITO website: www.eurito.eu

Time	Item	Speaker
9:30 - 10:30	Registration & Coffee	
10:30 - 10:40 <i>(10 mins)</i>	1. Opening remarks	1. Marta Truco-Colbert, DG Research & Innovation Unit A4
10:40 - 10:55 <i>(15 mins)</i>	2. Opening of the Workshop Presentation of the EURITO project, aims of the workshop, high level matrix of the pilots and note on ethical considerations of data use.	2. Chantale Tippet and Joel Klinger (Nesta)
10:55 - 11:55 <i>(1 hr)</i>	3. Morning Presentations Wave 1 Pilots <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pilot 1 Emergent technology ecosystems, AI (Nesta) 2. Pilot 2 Nowcasting business R&D (led by Nesta with input from COTEC) 3. Pilot 3 Technological change indicators, bioenergy (DTU) 4. Pilot 4 Standards as indicators for the diffusion of innovation (Fraunhofer) 	<p>3.1 Juan Mateos-Garcia (Nesta)</p> <p>3.2 Alex Bishop and George Richardson (Nesta)</p> <p>3.3 Pedro Parraguez (DTU)</p> <p>3.4 Knut Blind (FH, Fraunhofer)</p>
11:55 - 12:25 <i>(30 mins)</i>	Select Participants' Case Studies 3 case studies of data-driven decision-making projects and initiatives as experience and lessons learnt. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data4Impact ● Web Mining of Firm Websites (ZEW) ● DARE (SPRU) 	<p>Vilius Stanciauskas, D4I</p> <p>Jan Kinne, ZEW</p> <p>Frédérique Bone, SPRU</p>

<p>12:25 - 13:25</p> <p>(1hr)</p>	<p>4. Morning Breakout Session</p> <p>Wave 1 Pilots</p> <p>Participants are grouped according to profile and experience in discussion groups distinguished by application domains covered in the pilots. Discussion group leads present a more detailed overview of wave 1 pilots, including pilot specification (research questions, data sources, methods, a risk register and a timeline) and the data, metadata and process infrastructure. Open discussion with participants for validation and feedback on pilot development, and crucially exploring the challenge of transferring from exploratory format to a concept of an indicator.</p> <p>Key considerations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the dataset (including sectoral and national representativity); ● Potential improvements in work processes, and potential adjustments to the content and schedule; ● How to transfer pilots from exploratory stage to a concept of an indicator; ● How to put in practice open-source philosophy, and invite/generate collaboration; ● Considerations for scale-up. 	<p>4. All</p>
<p>13:25 - 14:05</p>	<p>Lunch</p>	

<p>14:10 - 14:40</p> <p>(30 mins)</p>	<p>5. Open Floor Discussion gathering the Morning Breakout Session</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion group leads to give short recap of discussion points (according to key considerations and other findings) <i>max 5 mins each</i> • Questions/Comments from the floor <i>10 mins</i> 	<p>5. Presented by discussion group leads moderated by Chantale (Nesta)</p>
<p>14:40 - 15:10</p> <p>(30 mins)</p>	<p>6. Afternoon Presentation: Wave 2 Pilots</p> <p>Short presentation, referring back to High Level matrix. Presentation of aim of the afternoon session.</p> <p><i>Max 30 mins.</i></p>	<p>6. Juan and Pedro (Nesta & DTU)</p>
<p>15:10</p>	<p><i>Coffee in room</i></p>	
<p>15:10 - 16:10</p> <p>(1 hr)</p>	<p>7. Afternoon Breakout Session</p> <p>Using the Wave 2 Pilots as inspiration, the afternoon breakout session will be interactive and hands-on using EURITO-developed card decks.</p> <p>In two 30-minute sessions, participants are assigned discussion groups according to profile and will first, identify possible mini-pilots under the high-level specifications of wave 2 pilots and second, discuss core concepts according to the data pipeline of these mini-pilots: such as data collection, analysis and visualization, in addition to their policy-relevance.</p> <p>The aim is to experiment with creative methods of tackling both data pipeline and policy-relevant considerations using the EURITO card deck, but also to come up with interesting ideas for collaborative projects.</p>	<p>7. All</p>

<p>16:20 - 16:50</p> <p><i>(30 mins)</i></p>	<p>8. Floor Discussion and presentation of collaborative projects, aiming to have an overview of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative projects that can be developed noting the challenges and opportunities. 	<p>8. Presented by discussion group leads moderated by Chantale (Nesta)</p>
<p>16:50 - 17:10</p> <p><i>(20 mins)</i></p>	<p>9. Short Summary of Next Steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection criteria and scale-up 	<p>Juan Mateos-Garcia (Nesta)</p>

List of Participants

In alphabetical order:

Consortium Members

Fraunhofer FOKUS, Germany

- Prof. Dr. Knut Blind, Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems and Technische Universität Berlin, Faculty of Economics and Management, Chair of Innovation Economics

Fundación Cotec para la Innovación (Cotec), Spain

- Ainara Zubillaga, Director of Education and Training
- Aleix Pons, Director of Economy and Finance
- Ramón Xifré, "Economic policy" expert at "Los 100 de Cotec" network
- Eva Senra, "Statistics and Economic forecasting" expert at "Los 100 de Cotec" network
- Pilar Caro, Project Manager

Nesta, UK

- Alex Bishop, Principal Researcher in Data Science
- Chantale Tippett, Principal Researcher (Innovation Systems)
- George Richardson, Principal Researcher (Data Science)
- Joel Klinger, Data Developer
- Juan Mateos-Garcia, Head of Innovation Mapping, EURITO Technical and Scientific Project Coordinator
- Konstantinos Stathoulopoulos, Data Science Researcher
- Luca Bonavita, Data Visualisation Designer

Technical University of Denmark (DTU), Denmark

- Agzam Idrissov, PhD Fellow, Engineering Systems Division
- Pedro Parraguez, Postdoctoral Researcher, Engineering Systems Division

Research and Data-experts

- Alexander Feidenheimer, PhD Fellow and researcher, Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research (Fraunhofer ISI), Germany
- Amaia Martínez Muro, Iniciativas Estratégicas SPRI, Spain
- Andrea Bravo, Data visualisation expert, Denmark
- António Bob Santos, Board member, National Innovation Agency in Portugal (ANI)
- Barteld Braaksma, Statistics Netherlands, the Netherlands
- Fernando Galindo-Rueda, Senior Economist in the Economic Analysis and Statistics, Division of the OECD Directorate for Science, Technology and Industry, OECD.
- Frédérique Bone, Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU), University of Sussex, UK

- Haris Papageorgiou, Data Scientist at the Institute for Language and Speech Processing, Athena Research and Innovation Information Technologies (Athena RC), Greece
- Iason Demiros, Co-Founder, Qualia, Greece
- Jan Kinne, Centre for European Economic Research (ZEW), Mannheim, Germany
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- Tobias Buchmann, Center for Solar Energy and Hydrogen Research Baden-Württemberg (ZSW), Germany
- Vladimir Cvijanović, Senior Researcher, European Future Innovation System Centre (EFIS)
- Vilius Stančiauskas, Research Manager, Evaluation of Public Policies, Public Policy and Management Institute (PPMI), Lithuania

European Commission

- Elisa Boelman, Policy Analyst for Energy, Knowledge for the Energy, JRC
- Géraldine Joanny, data scientist, JRC DDG.3
- Marta Truco Calbet, Policy Officer, Country desk officer for Estonia and Ireland, DG RTD
- Paloma Martin, Project Adviser, REA and EURITO Project Officer
- Petros Gkotsis, Industrial Research and Innovation, JRC
- Roberta Pattono, Programme Officer - Research, B7 – Science with and for society, Gender Sector, DG RTD
- Sergio DiVirgilio, Team Leader - Business Intelligence & Advanced Analytics, DG RTD
- Yanaris Ortega García, Policy and Programme Data Analyst, DG RTD

Rapporteur's Summary

Ramon Xifré, COTEC

1. Goal of the workshop: the workshop in the context of the project

The “New Data for R&I Policy Workshop” (“Workshop”) is the last step of the scoping phase and one of the first steps in the exploration stage. The goal of the workshop was, on the one hand, to provide data-driven researchers with an opportunity to share their experiences and, on the other hand, to provide the project team with external inputs on how advance better the project by looking closely at the various pilots developed so far.

The workshop presented eight exploratory pilots, at various stages of concretion and development. The key goal of the workshop was to get constructive feedback from the audience about the content and approaches applied in the pilots, particularly regarding technical details, but also related to their policy relevance. The input obtained from the participants will contribute to make better informed decisions about these eight pilots, such as: Which are the most promising pilots to scale up in the next stage of the project? How to improve the specifications of the pilots? Which (i) data, (ii) analytical tools, and (iii) representations are better suited for each individual pilot?

The eight pilots were built by combining the original intuitions of the project consortium with the outcomes of three actions already undertaken in the project:

- Policy Maker Workshop (April 2018). It was oriented to gain first-hand insight from policymakers on both existing sets of indicators and their desires for a future generation of indicators (see Policy Maker Workshop report, published on May 11, 2018).
- Literature review. EURITO reviewed existing literature to identify the evidence needs of R&I policymakers along the policy cycle, from agenda setting to policy design, implementation and evaluation, as well as the history of data usage and the emerging opportunities offered by new data and analytics (see deliverable D 1.1 “The role of data in the R&I policy cycle”, 30 April 2018).
- Data Audit Exercise. It consists of a systematic analysis and indexing of accessible data sources potentially useful for defining the new set of indicators (see deliverable D 1.2, Audit of new R&I Data, released on June 1, 2018).

2. Structure and contents of the workshop

The core of the workshop consisted in the presentation and group discussion, in separate teams, of the eight pilots. The eight pilots were presented in two separate waves, each wave containing four pilots, with wave 2 pilots being more open in their design and less developed. The idea was to use feedback from wave 1 pilots to better define and implement wave 2 pilots.

Wave 1 – Morning session

Pilot 1. Emerging technology ecosystems, AI

Pilot 2. Nowcasting business R&D

Pilot 3. Technological change indicators, bioenergy

Pilot 4. Standards as indicators for the diffusion of innovation

Wave 2 – Evening session

Pilot 5. Evidence base for mission-drive R&I

Pilot 6. Advanced R&I funding analytics

Pilot 7. Inclusive innovation

Pilot 8. Knowledge exchange

The discussion of each pilot was structured following the data pipeline: from data collection, analysis and interpretation, to usage by decision makers.

As a preparation for the workshop, a [high-level matrix](#) was prepared. The matrix specifies, for each pilot: the general problem / challenge / opportunity; the main question that R&I is answering; the application domain and the key stakeholders; data sources; methods; and expected outputs.

In addition to the work related to the pilots, the workshop also included general information about the EURITO project for newcomers; a presentation on the ethical dimension of the project and how to address the ethical challenges; general information about the sister-project Data4Impact; and short presentation of case studies by some participants (Web Mining of Firm Websites and DARE-SPRU).

3. Main feedback obtained from the audience

The main general messages and conclusions that emerged from the workshop are here synthesized. For further information about the issues that emerged across the various discussions of the different pilots, see the notes prepared by the Lead Discussants of each pilot below.

- **Problem solving vs. unknown unknowns.** Some pilots (1, 3) are primarily developed by answering one or more specific questions regarding innovation activity in areas and/or industries. For this purpose, typically algorithms are used to look for a predefined set of keywords (and related concepts or patterns). This keeps the pilot focused and allows to provide very detailed information and/or visualizations. For instance: “In which EU cities / regions has been the R&I activity in AI more dynamic?” or “What is the rate and evolution of technological change in a given field X”? However, although this is a very valuable input, in certain cases, what would be worthier to know is precisely which are the “right questions” to ask or/and the “right keywords” to search for.
- **From descriptive to predictive.** The likelihood of transforming pilots from a purely descriptive exercise towards one with some predictive power is an important issue to consider. This was a central question for pilot 2 and to a lesser extent for pilots 1 and 3. Showing that the new generation of indicators improves the current set of indicators in this dimension might be useful to convince policymakers and the data community.
- **Simple, compatible indicators.** A winning strategy when proposing a new generation of indicators would be to position them as complements (or compatible) rather than substitutes of the existing sets of data. This indeed was also one of the key takeaways from the Policymakers’ Workshop in April. In practice, this seems to suggest that it is preferable that new indicators are simple in construction and rely on solid primary data. This appeared particularly in the discussion about pilot 4 and more moderately pilot 2. A corollary is that it might be useful, when considering a possible new indicator stemming from a given pilot, how the metadata (statistical specifications in terms of universe, sample, coverage, nomenclature, etc.) would look like.
- **Reconsideration of the concept of “impact” of R&D.** A general topic that emerged in the discussion of wave 2 pilots (pilots 5 – 8) was the issue, somehow abstract but of crucial importance, of defining properly the impact or outcome

of R&I beyond the purely economic dimension. In addition to economic returns, successful innovation can foster diversity in research teams, help address social missions and contribute to more inclusive communities, enhance knowledge exchanges that appear to be minor initially, but that may develop to become more substantial and relevant.

4. Next steps

As informed at the end of the workshop, the main next steps are the following:

- Based on the workshop feedback, completing the first wave of pilots.
- Further defining and implementing the second wave of pilots; this includes defining a strategy to get feedback for them.
- Deciding which pilots are going to be scaled up in the work package 3 of the project.
- Enriching the set of stakeholders (policy makers, data scientists & specialists, public officials, entrepreneurs, industry leaders, etc.) which can be consulted regarding the pilots.

Notes by Discussion Group Leaders

MORNING BREAKOUT SESSION

Pilot 1: Emerging technology

Juan Mateos-Garcia, Nesta, Head of Innovation Mapping, EURITO Technical and Scientific Project Coordinator

- **Applications**
 - Supporting an emerging technology discovery use case: How can EURITO help users to discover emerging technology trends they should be paying attention to and that they are not aware of yet?
 - Addressing various policy use cases: Emerging technologies are a moving target. Some policymakers are interested in the newest trends while others prefer to focus on diffusion into the mainstream. Should EURITO pilot address these two needs?
 - Classifying entities into basic and applied research: Are there any labelled datasets for classifying entities into different stages of research ranging from basic research over applied research to experimental development and/or technological readiness levels?
- **Data sources**
 - Integrating various data streams: EURITO is currently presenting the data in silos. Is EURITO planning to connect them? How?
 - Other data sources: incorporating regional data into the project.
 - Temporal consistency and biases: Open data sources available today may get closed or go out of fashion. How does EURITO deal with this? How does it account for the fact that appearing in an open platform such as GitHub is a strategic decision?
- **Implementation**
 - Dealing with variation in language: Different countries and sources will use different terminologies to refer to the same technology. How EURITO is planning to address this?
 - Dealing with evolution in terminology: Vocabularies related to a technology change over time. How are we planning to deal with this?
 - Training the models, e.g. models trained on generic corpora are more transferable but miss domain specific nuances.
 - Going beyond English: Are we planning to do this? It will be necessary if we decide to work with the Member State's research grant data. We could create a dictionary between languages e. g. using the EC translations, or use automatic translation services.
 - How to handle bad queries in Clio?
 - Do you propose alternatives?
 - Autocomplete?
 - Identify the topics in a document and apply proportions in every document returned?

Pilot 2: Nowcasting business R&D

Alex Bishop, Nesta, Principal Researcher in Data Science

George Richardson, Nesta, Principal Researcher in Data Science

- **Relevant projects/background:**
 - In Spain, attempts have been made to nowcast R&D expenditure
 - National account variables were the most successful predictors
 - In previous studies, public expenditure in R&D has also been a strong predictor of BERD investment
 - ERC nowcasting project
 - Explored variables such as employment
 - PDICD project could be relevant to review
 - JRC and Eurostat have had an ongoing dispute regarding BERD nowcasting
 - Eurostat has more data than they make publicly available as they have stringent criteria for quality
 - They have identified multiple gaps in R&D investment data (e.g. complete countries are missing certain sectors, etc.) which could be worth exploring in more depth. To date, these have been filled using a rule-based approach.
- **Data sources:**
 - Demand for skills through web scraping could be a promising avenue to explore
 - Debate about whether patents are an appropriate data source to use in a nowcasting model given their lag
 - Work to locate R&D labs at NUTS3 level could be helpful
 - Collaborations with universities, other companies
 - Commuting patterns/movement of people - how to deal with this?
 - ORBIS data
 - National policies/targets for Business Enterprise Expenditure on R&D (BERD) could potentially be included in the model
- **Implementation**
 - The level of aggregation at which the nowcasting is being conducted is important to consider, i.e. enterprise, OECD classifications of technology groups, sector, country, etc.
 - Models need to take into account the structural differences within countries, i.e. comparing Israel & Korea don't make sense if you don't account for sectoral composition
 - Multivariate models/indicators
 - Limited success in literature but has been tried with econometric models
 - R&D investment may have increased on sectoral level but be decreasing on company level due to concentration of R&D in large companies, like in Germany
 - Important to distinguish who "owns" spending of R&D funds vs. where it is

spent (e.g. R&D scoreboard spending in Austria may be “owned” by Germany)

- The added value of new data sources should be explored in more depth relative to what has been attempted/documentated in the literature

Pilot 3: Technological Change

Pedro Parraguez, DTU, Postdoctoral Researcher, Engineering Systems Division

- **Applications**

- Technological change patterns per country: part of the technological changes that the EURITO pilot is mapping might be connected to different stages of development, others might be connected to regional or organizational specialization. Since the pilot discloses the trajectories for each country, it might be also able to spot the nature of the differences between countries, e.g. the trajectories of developed countries VS developing countries; differences between different types of documents (e.g. patents vs publications). Pilot should aimed to define the implications for convergence and divergence of economical development as well as analysis of trajectories followed by different agents.
- From descriptive to predictive: Once enough tests and validation has been performed, it could be interesting to move into predictions of technological change given macro technological trajectories and micro term-term combinatorial patterns (e.g. from indirect to direct connections).

- **Data sources**

- Are there well-established ontologies? How difficult is to connect different ontologies in the required domains (biofuels/bioenergy)?
- It should be taken into account the delay between produced and released data across different data sources.

- **Implementation**

- Filter per data source: The importance of allowing to filter per data source so that the user/researcher can investigate the difference that might exist between different data-sources
- Time-lags of different data-sources: Different data-sources have their own timings, as a result, it is interesting to compare and try to align the “rhythms” of different data-sources
- How can we visualize hints/recommendations on what to explore? It might be useful to explore potential connections and recommendations for potential collaborations
- Evolution of networks over time
- Analyze whether similarity is affected by document types – i.e. documents from one data source can be dominating and skewing the results, e.g. publications may be focused on certain words, different from patents, so the EURITO pilot needs to be aware of and correct potential bias.

Pilot 4. Standards as indicators for the diffusion of innovation

Knut Blind, Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems and Technische Universität Berlin

- **Applications**
 - Link between innovation and standardisation. It has been pointed out that standards can restrict innovation. However, the empirical studies show this ambivalence in the inverted U-shape between R&D or innovation intensity and the likelihood or intensity of companies' participation in standardisation. Furthermore, it has to be acknowledged that standards promote in general only incremental, but not radical innovations. However, examples like the USB or the GSM standards have been the basis for the development of complete new markets, e.g in mobile communication.
 - Distinction between the management and the technical standards. Whereas the technical standards are sector specific, the presented management standards can be in general applied across all sectors confirming the general focus on the pilot. In addition, management standards are not restricting innovation in companies, whereas some technical standards, like interfaces, provide itself no leeway for innovation.
- **Data sources**
 - Availability of data. Whereas the availability of information about the participation within standardisation is limited, the data provided about the number of certificates of international management standards differentiated by country and sector is public available.
 - Necessary reassessment of quality management to regain certifications in companies. It could be the case that some companies lose their certification. Related to the web scraping, companies could still leave a reference to certificates on international management standards on their homepage, although they have failed to regain the certificate. However, it was argued that this is an illegal deception of customers. Overall, the investigation of initial certifications and even the loss of certifications could be the basis of company-based panel analyses and even allows the construction of diffusion patterns, in particular of recently released management standards, like IT security or energy efficiency management.
- **Implementation**
 - Public organisations are also implementing standards and require the certification of their management processes. Although the certification data cover all sectors, certifications related to public or non-for-profit organisations are the exception. As an example it has been mentioned that in public private partnerships an alignment of management processes is necessary, which could be facilitated by harmonized certification processes.
 - It is suggested to investigate companies' motivations for certification to provide a broader basis for using certifications as indicators.
 - As a minor point, the language of companies' web-pages could be a signal whether companies are focusing on export markets.

AFTERNOON BREAKOUT SESSION (WAVE 2)

Pilot 5: Evidence base for mission-driven R&I (Nesta)

- **Considerations for application**
 - Defining missions: When does a mission start and how broad it is? Missions can be defined at the level of society, specific challenges or projects. Different questions are relevant for the different levels. For example, understanding how social needs are articulated into missions relates to the societal level; understanding what the best language is to define a challenge relates to the project level.
 - The above also relates to the metrics we use to define impacts. Societal missions / challenges are often vague in the metrics that will be used to assess success, so EURITO might have to decide what they are. Narrower missions tend to make their goals operational, so we could use them to assess success.
- **Data sources**
 - Generality vs breadth: Is there a one-size-fits-all infrastructure for data collection and analysis? Missions have very varied goals, from reducing youth debt to removing plastic from the oceans. Although there are some shared datasets EURITO could use to understand capabilities and activities around specific mission areas, it may need completely different data sources to measure impacts. In some cases, the relevant data will only be available in proprietary / closed sources (e.g. banks in the case of youth debt) so accessing it will be difficult.
 - Developing an extensive template to build mission evidence bases: it was discussed the idea of running a pilot on a specific mission. Some of its components (e.g. data sources, analysis, visualisations) may be applicable to all missions while others would be mission specific.
 - Social media biases: EURITO should be careful if it uses social media data, given its significant participation biases.
- **Applications**
 - Predictive analyses: There was strong interest on the development of tools or platforms that help predict the likelihood that a given project / team will be able to address a mission or challenge, and of the language for challenges which is more conducive to successful projects.

Pilot 6: Advanced R&I funding analytics (Nesta)

- **Considerations for application**
 - Many potential levels to measure: Project vs. institution vs. sector
 - What constitutes success on an institutional level? Excellence in specific areas vs. contributions to a breadth of research
 - Different indicators by subject are required
 - The goal of the funding organisation needs to be taken into account when deciding what/how to measure
- **Potential predictors of success**
 - Team diversity is completely overlooked in current assessments

- Big players/experienced players/well connected players are probably a big predictor of success
- Market environment around the subject matter - how ready the “market” is to absorb the technology that is being developed will be a factor.
- **Gaps**
 - It would be nice to get counter-factual data and see what projects are not funded, or projects that were funded but unsuccessful.
 - What happens after the completion of a project? No-one has really looked at this much? (Tracking what happens to teams & project development over time)
 - Cross-sectional impact is a missing measure of success - an output could have impact in another sector. (This could also be a process or a skill too)
- **Miscellaneous**
 - Reference to <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/innovation-radar-new-policy-tool-support-innovation-management> in the context of assessing “innovation of innovators”. The methodology has 5 dimensions: market, tech readiness, management, etc. The difficulty is how to assess subjective things such as diversity.
- **Data sources:**
 - LEIDEN rankings - <http://www.leidenranking.com/>
 - H2020 dashboard - <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/projectresults/index.html>
 - CEDEFOP - <http://www.cedefop.europa.eu/>
 - LinkedIn
 - CORDIS - https://cordis.europa.eu/home_en.html
 - Finland market opportunities (+similar) - <https://team.finland.fi/en/services/market-opportunities>
 - ORBIS - <https://www.bvdinfo.com/en-gb/our-products/data/international/orbis>
 - Online job ads
 - Patent classes pertaining to different H2020 Societal Grand Challenges (SGC’s) - Frietsch et al. 2016, Fraunhofer ISI Discussion Papers Innovation Systems and Policy Analysis, No. 53 <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/46122872.pdf>

Pilot 7: Inclusive Innovation (Nesta)

- **Considerations for application / data sources**
 - Including society in R&I is an important but perhaps underappreciated dimension of inclusiveness
 - Citizen science - indicators could be developed around means of engagement, intensity of engagement, topics, participants, citizens included in patents, papers
 - Citizen engagement is going to gain increasing prominence in FP9, so having a better grasp of this landscape would be powerful
 - Ways people are talking about R&I topics in social media and other media

- Sentiment analysis on different topics
- Inclusive *inputs* in business and academia
 - Inclusiveness of teams (e.g. gender, ethnicity)
 - Employee composition (e.g. gender, ethnicity)
- Inclusive *outputs* in business and academia
 - Inclusiveness within Business enterprise sector (BES) in terms of products (e.g. who are products being designed for?)
 - Further exploration of inclusiveness in traditional outputs (e.g. publications, patents)
 - An indicator already exists that explores the gender dimension in research content, but to our knowledge no such indicator exists for patents or products
- Inclusiveness of policies
 - For example, the data on gender equality plans within universities is currently collected via survey but the data have much room for improvement. A web scraping approach could theoretically be an option for trying to collect this.
 - The OECD's STIP database contains policies from multiple countries. It could be interesting to use a combination of Natural language processing (NLP) and/or crowd coding to explore how inclusiveness and equity issues are being discussed.
- Positions of authority
 - For example, Grade A in the higher education sector is a key indicator for tracking gender equality in the Higher education sector (HES) - a 'grade A' equivalent for BES would be interesting.
- Trajectories and mobility
 - It would be possible to explore the 'trajectories' of people within the RI system using data sources such as Orcid and Crunchbase.
 - Movement of women/men researchers currently captured in MORE2 survey, but there is room for improvement
 - Unclear whether indicators exist on the movement of entrepreneurs, and whether these have an inclusivity dimension
 - Awareness and other metrics of quality of life (e.g. social policies, childcare options) would be important for interpreting findings
- Combining multiple dimensions of the above and performing geographical analyses would provide a deeper insight into location-based challenges and opportunities for inclusive RI

Pilot 8: Knowledge/information exchange and linkages (DTU)

- **Applications**
 - Research impact can also be measured analysing the number of representatives of particular research communities in documents. For example, number of people affiliated to editorial boards of journals, ministries, committees, etc.
- **Data sources**
 - Is it possible to put the same level of trust in different data sources (e.g. cannot compare patent data with newspaper articles)?
 - Investigate the exploration of collaborations that are happening outside of formally captured innovative networks as informal collaborations (e.g.

meetings in conferences or other events, shared membership in different committees).

- Try to connect new data sources with related contextual information like economic indicators, e.g. connect publications on certain topics with traditional statistics on those topics (e.g. manufacturing or infrastructure statistics).
- Web scraping can be applied to find connections between companies through hyperlinks
- Take into account shared references and institutions as well

- **Implementation**

- Knowledge does not have to flow through only one channel – it may spread across multiple routes. On the other hand, multiple links might be redundant in scientific research. As a result it is not immediately obvious the best technique that should be used to quantify the strength of multiple ties.
- Important to distinguish the types of links or connection in order to be able to quantify the general intensity or impact of a given relation. For instance, similar links tend not to facilitate knowledge flow.
- Suggestion not only to consult with domain experts, but then disseminate knowledge to the general audience as well.

